

NDAC/LO/085

1986, Oct 24

NDAC simulations of double and multiple stars:
Detectability and astrometric accuracy (*)

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(*) to be presented at the 3rd FAST Thinkshop, Bari, Nov 3-6, 1986

1. Introduction

The outstanding "problem objects" in the HIPPARCOS reductions are the double and multiple stars. Using several different criteria, these "trouble stars" have to be flagged and excluded from the main reductions. Special post-mission procedures are then used to extract as much information as possible about them.

Before writing the software for these final reductions, we are making rather extensive simulations and test programs. The present paper discusses some main results from these tests, further details may be found in Refs. 1-6.

2. Observation simulation

For a given "trouble object", a mission and instrument model gives the complete set of IDT observations. The scanning is "schematic" (gaussian deviations from the nominal, no eclipse interruptions), but for the present purpose it should suffice. The instrument model uses the large-scale grid distortion and a detailed OTF-model including colour-dependent modulation amplitudes and phase errors. For each frame where the object is observed, the individual IDT-counts are calculated, but they are preprocessed directly to five Fourier coefficients (and their mean errors). These five parameters per frame are the basic data used by the the different analysis programs. (For wide doubles, the IFOV pointing may be different for the two components. In this case, ten parameters per frame are obtained, five for each pointing.) See also Ref. 7.

3. Reduction principles

The real analysis is made after the main reductions are completed, thus a "true" reference phase and the exact scan-geometry are available. The only unknowns are the parameters describing the multiple object, and a standard non-linear iterative least squares adjustment of these parameters are made with the IDT Fourier coefficients as "observations".

The differential coefficients $\partial(\text{Fourier coeff.})/\partial(\text{model parameter})$ may be calculated analytically, as also a simple weighting that takes the IFOV pointing and -profile into account. (In particular, a bright component near the edge of the IFOV gives poor data for the centered faint one.) Both theoretically and in practice, it is advantageous to use only the first and second harmonic amplitudes and phases, not the total intensity. In the real reductions, these Fourier coefficients will be averaged over each FOV-passage, but in the test runs, there are four coefficients per frame, 4704 in all for a "typical" position at latitude 32° .

The main difficulty is to find start values for the model parameters that ensure a convergent LS-process. Either one has to know (within some $0''.2$) the positions of all the components, or one may iterate also the start values. When the start values are good enough, the least squares process converges in 5-10 iterations, giving final estimates for the astrometric parameters. In the simulation tests, the estimated parameters may be compared with the true (input) ones to give a measure of the astrometric accuracy. See further below.

4. Known doubles and multiples

For known double or n-tuple stars (with linear orbital motion over 2.5 years), an obvious 6n-parameter model (five astrometric parameters and a magnitude for each component) may be used. For wide doubles ($\text{sep} > 2''$), a priori positions within $0''.3$ are enough; for closer ones, or for multiples, $0''.1$ is sometimes required for convergence. The astrometric accuracy of the resulting solution may be conveniently specified (for one component or for the photocentre) by

$$\text{rms}(\text{astr}) = \left[\frac{1}{5} \{ (x_s - x_t)^2 + (y_s - y_t)^2 + (\pi_s - \pi_t)^2 + (\dot{x}_s - \dot{x}_t)^2 + (\dot{y}_s - \dot{y}_t)^2 \} \right]^{1/2} \quad (1)$$

where subscripts s and t stand for solution and true, and where a yearly proper motion is given equal weight as a position.

Such astrometric rms-errors have been determined for a variety of systems (cf. Refs. 1,2,4,6), and for doubles, the variation with separation may be summarized as follows. The astrometric error is about constant in the range 0.3-5", increases to a maximum at 15 arcsec, and then levels off again at 25-35". Some mean results for equal-magnitude systems are shown in Fig. 1. For "trapezium type"-multiples, (separations 2-7" between nearest neighbours), the astrometric errors are only somewhat larger than for similar doubles. The "total weight" Σrms^{-2} for an n-tuple diminishes with n, but only to about 2/3 at n=5 vs n=2.

The important comparison of these actual astrometric errors with those given by the inverse NE matrix shows no gross inconsistencies. The real errors are larger than the formal ones by only about 20%.

5. Double star detection

For a large number of previously unknown binaries, the goodness-of-fit measures accumulated during the regular processing will indicate probable multiplicity. In order to determine the parameters for these suspected binaries, it is necessary to make an extra "grid iteration" of the standard LS process. If we do not get convergence with one assumed separation/PA, another is tried from a grid of twelve (four points at sep=0"35, eight at sep=0"85. Fortunately, the intensities act linearly in the observation equations, thus a start value 1.0 for the magnitude difference between the components always works). The definition of convergence may be delicate. One has to select a maximum χ^2 error for the fit to the observations, below which an apparently convergent solution is accepted. Solutions with slightly poorer fit are saved until all grid-points have been tested, and only then the minimum is selected.

To test this "discovery mode", a number of quasi-realistic binaries have been generated. For given magnitudes, separation and period, a binary with consistent masses, colours and distance is created, and its exact orbital positions is used in the simulation program. For comparison with the standard analysis results, a linear approximation to the individual positions and proper motions is also given. (In practice, very few systems will give problems due to nonlinear orbital motion, cf. Ref. 5.) With guidance from the results in Ref. 8, a uniform distribution over $\lg \text{sep}$ and a corresponding gaussian $\lg P$ distribution (mean $\lg P(\text{years})=3.3+1.5*\lg \text{sep}(\text{"})$) was assumed for three different values of the primary H-magnitude,

and several hundred test binaries were generated.

The analysis is made in two steps. First, a single-star solution is made, and then the double-star grid search. The output from either is a goodness-of-fit χ^2 measure S (ideally with nobs d.o.f.), and secondly the actual astrometric errors as compared with the true values. With regard to S , one may divide the solutions into three groups:

$$1(s) : S(\text{sing}) < S_1, S(\text{sing}) - S(\text{bin}) < s_1$$

$$2(b) : S(\text{sing}) - S(\text{bin}) > s_1$$

$$3(p) : S(\text{sing}) > S_1, S(\text{sing}) - S(\text{bin}) < s_1$$

The actual values for S_1 and s_1 may be adjusted; for the standard case nobs=4704 I have used mostly $S_1=5000$, $s_1=400$. Neglecting the small p ("problem") category, we may say that useful binary parameters are obtained for the b ("binary") category, while a single-star solution is sufficient for the s ("single") systems. (Some of the p-stars may safely be added to the singles because of unrealistic sep/dH-values.)

The b/s-distinction is so far based only on the χ^2 fit to the observations. For the best-studied case (8.5 mag primary, 32° latitude), Fig. 2 gives a plot of the b- and s-stars in the (lg sep/ Δm)-plane. A good division is given by the straight lines indicated. For separations above some $0''.32$, we have a $dH_{\text{max}}=3.4$ such that systems with larger magnitude difference are observed as singles. For smaller separations, the border-line is taken simply as

$$dH = 5.5 \lg \text{sep} + 6.12 \quad (2)$$

down to a minimum separation about $0''.11$ - $0''.12$. Systems with smaller separations will not be discovered as double, even at $dH=0$.

It might be assumed that $dH_{\text{max}}=3.4$ is due to a magnitude cut-off at $H_{\text{sec}}=8.5+3.4=12$. Fig. 3 gives the b/s-plot for systems with $H_{\text{pr}}=6.0$, but the increase is only to about $dH_{\text{max}}=4.2$, $\text{sep}_{\text{min}}=0.10$ arcsec. Thus, even for bright stars, a secondary more than about 4.2 magnitudes fainter than its primary will go unnoticed. There is of course a real magnitude limit as seen for $H_{\text{pr}}=11.0$ in Fig. 4. Here, as expected, no secondary below $H=13.5$ is detected, and the minimum separation is about $0''.17$.

Figs. 2-4 are all for a position on the sky at ecliptic latitude 32° . The analogue of Fig. 2 at latitude 12° is shown as Fig. 5. The "standard"

border of Fig. 2 is indicated, and it appears thus that the effect of different scan-geometries is relatively minor.

The above dH - and separation-limits are significantly worse than the estimates by Lindegren in Ref. 9. The reason for this is unclear, but it should be noted that some s-systems do give good double solutions. In reality, this double solution will never be attempted, because the single-star fit is too good.

6. Astrometric errors

As to the actual astrometric errors, there are several points to be made. For the s-systems, a single-star solution may be compared with either the primary component or with the photocentre. The latter is the obvious choice for a close double, but the former is more adequate for a well-separated system with a large magnitude difference. Barring the somewhat difficult intermediate region (0.2-0.4 arcsec), the single star rms-errors (eq. 1) are in the range 1-3 mas (depending on magnitude). The only significant discrepancies are for a few short-period astrometric pairs.

For the b-systems, the astrometric parameters for the photocentre are almost always well determined, while the relative coordinates for the two components are increasingly difficult to disentangle as the separation shrinks and/or the magnitude difference increases. Eq. (2) for the b/s-border suggests that one introduces the "effective magnitude difference"

$$\begin{aligned} dH_{\text{eff}} &= dH - 5.5 \lg(\text{sep}/0.32) & \text{sep} < .32 \\ dH_{\text{eff}} &= dH & \text{sep} > .32 \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

There is then a clear relation between dH_{eff} and the relative rms-error (see Fig. 6), which may be approximated by quadratic relations

$$\text{rms}(\text{rel}) = C_1 + C_2 * (dH_{\text{eff}})^2 \quad (4)$$

Typical values for C_1 and C_2 are given in Table 1. The astrometric errors for the photocentre may also be of some interest. They increase somewhat for large separations, thus the values given in Table 1 are for $\text{sep} < 0.4$ arcsec.

Table 1. Typical effective errors for the four "classes" of binaries in Figs. 2-5.

H_{pr}	lat	obstime(sec)	C_1 (mas)	C_2 (mas)	rms _{pc} (mas)
8.5	32°	502	1.2	0.8	0.7
6.0	32°	251	0.9	0.6	0.5
11.0	32°	502	3.4	1.6	1.8
8.5	12°	389	1.8:	0.8:	0.8

All the above concerns the astrometric parameters. It is also interesting to look briefly at the magnitudes. For several reasons (IDT profile, binning etc.), the observed intensities tend to be somewhat low, and there will also be complicated colour-effects. These "absolute" deviations are not in themselves important, what matters is the double star magnitudes as compared with the (standardized) values for singles. Using only the mean magnitude deviations (sol-true) for primary components (sep>0".4) and photocentre (sep<".2), we find a systematic "magnitude-equation" of size 0.^m014/mag for the binaries, 0.^m019/mag for the singles. There remains a barely significant differential error of 0.^m005/mag, which may not be eliminated by the use of (single) photometric standards. (Typical magnitude standard deviations are about 0.^m02-0.^m03 in the range H_{pr} =6-11.)

The magnitude-differences given in the double solutions have small errors for $dH_{eff} < 2$. (Typical standard deviation 0.01 for H_{pr} =6 to 0.07 for H_{pr} =11). For larger dH_{eff} , the standard deviation is more often around 0.10 mag. A possible magnitude equation is of the same (0.^m005/mag) size as above.

7. Triple star detection

The method of Section 5 for finding unknown binaries may be adapted to handle the case of an unknown third component to a known wide double. A poor observation fit to the assumed binary configuration may indicate a resolvable third component, and one may start then a double iteration search for its parameters. Only a few test runs have been made as yet, and the preliminary findings are as follows.

The simulated configuration is a 15 arcsec binary with equal components attended by a close component (0".1-1".0 arcsec separation, 0-3^m magnitude difference). The solution program first makes a double solution and then a

triple star solution with iterated start parameters. The parameters for the third component were found correctly in a similar area of the $sep/\Delta m$ -plane as in the single/double case. The exact limits (in this particular case!) are not well-determined, but are around $dH_{\max} = 2.5$, $sep_{\min} = 0''.13$. (When the third star is assumed to be near the wrong wide component, an obviously false solution far from both stars is obtained.)

It is difficult to estimate the proportion of thus discoverable triples among the wide binaries, but the method proposed will certainly be useful in some cases.

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Fig. 1 (Astrom. errors for equal-mag. systems)

Fig 2. (8.5 primary, lat 32 deg)

Fig 3. (8.0 primary, lat 32 deg)

Fig 4. (11.0 primary, lat 32 deg)

Fig 5. (8.5 primary, lat 12 deg)

Fig 6. (8.5 primary, lat 32 deg)

Fig. 1. Mean astrometric errors for the components in equal-magnitude systems of different brightness. Typical error-bars indicated at right.

Figs. 2-4. Effective border-lines between singles and doubles in the $\lg \text{ sep} / \Delta m$ -plane. Slope of inclined part is 5.5 mag per dex.

Fig. 5. Border from Fig. 2 (lat 32°) superposed on the data for lat 12° .

Fig. 6. Relative astrometric error (companion-primary) as function of dH_{eff} .